
Common errors in geo-ontology engineering

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Ontology engineering—the systematic design of machine-readable vocabularies or ontologies—has a long history in GI science. The promise of such “geo-ontologies” is to provide solutions to some of the most long-standing challenges in the field, such as semantic interoperability; tracking provenance and metadata; and capturing enormous richness of geospatial data and phenomena with simple and consistent representations. Recent rapid advances in large language models (LLMs) have provided renewed impetus for geo-ontology engineering, because knowledge-based representation and reasoning offers structural and logical characteristics that complement the strengths of LLMs for pattern-matching unstructured data. However, geo-ontology engineering is fraught with pitfalls and snares. Errors are frequent, especially for less-experienced ontology engineers. This paper argues that three key errors are most commonly encountered, including in papers in the domain of geographic information science. The paper explores in more detail these three types errors, illustrated through the example of engineering a geo-ontology for update and revision of foundation spatial data (SMURF, the spatial management, update, and revision framework) within a recent project in partnership with state-based mapping agency (the “Dynamic Vicmap” project). In brief, the three key errors relate to ontology reuse, clarity, and consistency. Reuse is a core principle of ontology engineering, which enables ontologies to be more modular and standardized, and data to be more easily linked together. Clarity relates to avoiding errors in definition, such as misclassifying instances as classes. Consistency relates to avoiding internal contradictions, and most concerns the domain-specific judgements

embodied in a geo-ontology, such as deciding whether an entity is best represented as an instance or attribute. Examples of each type of error are illustrated with reference to the SMURF geo-ontology, engineered to represent and link multiple statewide hydrology, property, and flood event data sets reusing established ontology standards, including GeoSPARQL, PROV-O and DCAT.

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